

DR. B. R. AMBEDKAR'S VIEWS ON WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH CONSTITUTIONAL PROVISIONS

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In ancient India, women enjoyed a very high position but gradually their position degenerated into merely objects of pleasure serve certain purpose. They lost their individual identity and their basic human rights. Women empowerment is a process in which women gained greater share of control over resources material, human and intellectual like knowledge information, ideas and financial resources like money-and access to money and control over decision making in the home, community, society and the nation and to gain power. In Hindu Shastras, women had been branded just like animals or like some objects of enjoyment. In Manu Smriti, the ancient Hindu codebook, the status granted to women is quite visible and she was put to the rung of humanity as she was treated at par with the animals and slaves by the properties of the Hindu Dharma. Such was the placement earmarked to our mothers, sisters and even great grandmothers that humanity was ashamed of. That is why Dr. Ambedkar, the Father and Architect of the Indian Constitution, was of the firm opinion that until and unless we defy the Hindu Dharmashastras, nothing much could be changed.

Dramatic changes have taken place in the legal, political, educational and social status of women since independence .This was not unexpected since the question of the improvement of the position of women had been at the heart of the social reform movement from the first quarter of the nineteenth century when Ram Mohan Roy started his questioning of social orthodoxy. Besides, the freedom struggle since the twenties and especially since the thirties had partaken amply ample of the creative energies of Indian women.

Gandhiji's statement in the mid thirties to Mridula Sarabhai, a valiant fighter for his causes of women and freedom, 'I have brought the Indian women out of the kitchen, it is up to you (the women activities) to see that they don't go back,'¹ was no empty boast and no thoughtless exhortation. The national movement by treating women as political beings capable of nationalist feelings and as if not more, capable of struggle and sacrifice than men resolved many doctrinal debates about the desirability of women's role in the public sphere. If women could march in processions, defy the laws, go to jail- all unescorted by male family members- then they could also aspire to take up jobs, have the right to vote, and maybe even inherit parental property. Political participation by women in the massive popular struggles from the twenties onwards opened up new vistas of possibilities that a country of social reform could not. The image of a woman changed from a recipient of justice in the nineteenth century, to an ardent supporter of nationalist men in the early twentieth century, to a comrade by the thirties and the forties. Women had participated in all streams of the national movement- from Gandhian to Socialist to Communist to revolutionary terrorist. They had been in peasant movements and in trade union struggles. They had founded separate women organizations as well; the All India Women's Conference, founded in 1926, being the most important of these. After independence, when the time came to consolidate the gains of the hard fought struggle, the attention naturally turned to securing legal and constitutional rights. The constitution promised complete equality to women. It fulfilled the promise made many years ago by the national movement: women got the vote, along with men, without any qualification of education or income or property. A right for which women suffragettes fought long and hard in many western countries was won at one stroke by Indian women!

In the early fifties, Nehru initiated the process of the enactment of the Hindu code bill, a measure demanded by women since the thirties. A Committee under the Chairmanship of B.N. Rau, the constitutional expert who prepared the first draft of the constitution of India, had already gone into the matter and submitted a draft code in 1944.

Another Committee chaired by B.R. Ambedkar, the law minister after independence, submitted a bill which raised the age of consent and marriage, upheld monogamy, gave women the rights to divorce, maintenance and inheritance and treated dowry as stridhan/women's property. Strong opposition from the conservative sections of the society and hesitation on the part of some senior congress leaders, including President Rajendra Prasad, led to the bill being postponed, despite strong support from a majority of congressmen and women activists and social reformers, ultimately, sections of the bill were

passed as four separate acts-the Hindu Marriage Act, the Hindu Succession Act, the Hindu Minority and Guardianship Act and the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act.

Dr Ambedkar – the determined fighter and a deep scholar has made significant efforts to lead the society on the path of Liberty, Equality and Fraternity. He laid the foundation of concrete and sincere efforts by codifying the common civil code for Hindus and the other sections of the Indian society.

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar was among the most outstanding intellectuals of India in the 20th century in the word ,Paul Barn ,an eminent Marxist Economist ,had made a distinction in one of his essays between an “intellect worker “.

Dr. B.R. Ambedkar is also an outstanding example of what Antonio Gramsci called an organic intellectual, that is, one who represents and articulates the interest of an entire social class. Ambedkar was not only the father of Indian Constitution: he was a great freedom fighter political leader, philosopher, thinker, economist, editor, social reformer, revivalist of Buddhism and was first Indian to break down the barriers in the way of advancement of women in India.

Dr Ambedkar championed the cause of women as well as the miserable plight of Schedule Castes and Scheduled Tribes throughout his career .he discussed number of problems of Indian women and sought for their solutions in Bombay Legislative Council, in the Viceroy’s Assembly as the chairman of the Drafting committee.

Dr Ambedkar was sworn in as a nominated member of the Bombay Legislative Council on 18th Feb, 1927.He advised Indians to participate in the world war on behalf of the British Government .His argument on the Maternity Benefit Bill and on Birth Critical were quite relevant to recognize the dignity of women .He vehemently supported the Maternity Bill.

His argument was –

“It is in the interest of the nation that the mother ought to get a certain amount of rest during the pre-natal period and also subsequently, and the principal of the Bill is based entirely on that principal.

“That being so sir, I am bound to admit that the burden of this ought to be largely borne by the government, I am prepared to admit this fact because of the conservation of the people’s welfare is primary concern of the Government .And in every country, you will find that government has been subjected to a certain amount of charge with regarded to maternity benefit. “

Ambedkar's Idea of Equality-

He incorporated the values of Liberty, Equality and Fraternity in the Indian Constitution. Based on the belief that any scheme of franchise and constituency that fails to bring about representation of opinions as well as representation of people falls short of creating a popular government, he submitted the Constitution with a warning. He said in his speech delivered in the Constituent Assembly on 25th November, 1949, "Political Democracy cannot last unless there lies at the base of its social democracy". By social he means a way of life which recognized Liberty, Equality and Fraternity as a principle of life. He further said on 26th of January, 1950, "We are going to enter a life of contradictions. In Politics we will have equality, and a social and economic life."

Constitutional Provisions-

The Constitution of India contains various provisions which provide for equal rights and opportunities for both men and women. The salient features are-

- Article 14 Guarantee that the State shall not deny equality before the law and equal protection of the laws.
- Article 15 Prohibits discrimination against any citizen on the ground of sex.
- Article 15/3 Empowers the state to make positive discrimination in favour of women and children.
- Article 16 Provides for equal opportunity in matters of public employment.
- Article 23 Prohibits trafficking in humans and forced labour.
- Article 39 A and B Enjoin the state to provide equal means of livelihood and equal pay for equal work.
- Article 42 Enjoins upon the state to make provisions just and human conditions of work and for maternity relief.
- Article 51 A/E Imposes a fundamental duty on every citizen to renounce the practices derogatory to the dignity of women.
- Article 243 D/3 Provides that not less than 1/3rd of the total number of seats to be filled by direct elections in Panchayats to be reserved for women.

In pursuance of the above constitutional provisions, various legislative enactments have been framed to protect, safeguard and promote the interest of women. Many of these legislative enactments have been in the sphere of labour laws to ameliorate the working conditions of women labour.

Conclusion-

Thus, if the legal and political rights granted to women in the Constitution, which are theirs by virtue of their own efforts as well as by all norms of social justice, are to be realized and democratized, millions of women have to become capable of understanding and exercising them. Kerala and Himachal Pradesh, at two poles of the country, have shown the way: the heartland has to follow. The women's movement also needs to incorporate education and health as priorities into its strategies for women's empowerment

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